

Household 3D Cream Printer for Cake Decoration

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Self-Introduction

- Grade 11 student at Branksome Hall, Canada
- Maker: 7 years of STEAM learning and experience: 3D CAD design & programming & graphic design
- Robotics, 3D design; sketching; baking; photography

2016 – Beijing IxDM interaction Design Marathon Maker Challenge

2017 – MEV Technology Challenge 1st International Competition

2017 - F1 in Schools Technology Challenge World Finals

2018 – Design 3D-printed school logo

Background

- 3D printers have become widely available as consumer electronics
- A labor-intensive task that requires a significant amount of skills
- Household 3D Cream Printer for Cake Decoration

Home 3D Printer [\[ref\]](#)

Hand-made Cake Decoration [\[ref\]](#)

Existing Solutions and Challenges

- Existing food 3D printers: chocolate, candy (relative hard materials)
- Challenges: the material is very soft and difficult to shape into the desired geometry; exquisite appearance requires multicolor printing.

3D-printed Chocolate [\[ref\]](#)

3D-printed Candy [\[ref\]](#)

Cream [\[ref\]](#)

Objective

- The system is designed to print with cream, produce multiple materials/colors and be affordable (hundreds of dollars).

Process

1. A 3-axis motion system: Creality Ender 3 Pro
2. A material extruder: realization of cream extrusion
3. Control algorithms: material selection and 3D design slicer
4. An environment control chamber: cream cooling

Results & Future Work

Current Stage

- Successfully extrude cream
- Investigating the effects of temperature and other printing parameters

Future Work

- Multi-color printing through one nozzle
- More complex geometries